

The blessing of peace in the new Uzbekistan is thanks to our happiness

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Abstract: This article focuses on the positive changes and reforms being carried out in New Uzbekistan. The fact that today's citizens value our peace is covered in detail.

When we look at the prospects of our children studying in the peaceful and peaceful conditions of today, we involuntarily remember the recent past. We remember that during the time of the former Soviets, which shook half of the world with its millions of soldiers and terrible military equipment, there was no peace among the citizens. Maybe the existence of such an army did not give people peace. We may not have realized that peace is a peaceful condition like the flight of a bird in the sky. Today, when our streets are smooth, our days are peaceful, and our nights are bright, we began to feel more deeply that the great blessing of peace cannot be solved with weapons until the tip of the nail, and that this is the result of the government's rational policy. Now, if we bring to our eyes our children who are receiving education in prosperous educational institutions all over the country in such peaceful conditions, we feel the joy of confidence in the future. After all, it is no exaggeration to say that the fate of development in the 21st century will be decided in the family and educational institutions.

At the ceremony dedicated to the twenty-fourth anniversary of our independence, our 1st president spoke about the importance of independence and said: "It is valuable and prestigious because it freed our country and people from the shackles of the old autocratic system, built a national democratic state, and opened the way to establish a prosperous life equal to all countries and peoples."

In fact, thanks to this priceless blessing, our ancient traditions and values were restored, the whole world knew and recognized that we are descendants of great people, our cities and villages became beautiful, our country became prosperous, and the standard and quality of life of our people increased. Such positive changes continue consistently. In other words, Uzbekistan is boldly climbing the ladder of development on the way to become one of the most developed democratic countries. Today, the world community looks with great envy at another aspect of our country, that is, the mutual kindness and harmony of our people, our nation. These factors have a special place in the stability of the peace and tranquility prevailing in our country, in the fulfillment of the intended goals and tasks.

Uzbekistan took the 44th place among 158 countries in the "Global Happiness Index", the first place among the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States. The more times we say this information, the more valuable it is. Because it gives us infinite pride and honor.

In fact, it is not an easy task to maintain the inviolability of borders and build a prosperous life in the current era of globalization, where various threats and contradictions have increased, and borderless dangers are on the rise. We must not forget, even for a moment, that it is our sacred duty to draw the right conclusions from them, to live always awake and alert, to appreciate our clear sky, to protect it like the apple of our eye.

In the words of Islam Karimov, Uzbekistan is a sacred Motherland for all of us, the land of our ancestors. We are all happy that raising our children in the spirit of loyalty to this land,

instilling in their hearts affection and love for every old person of this blessed land, is becoming one of the most important tasks of today. At the same time, loyalty to the Motherland and national pride became the meaning of our lives in our way of life and in our understanding of the essence of independence. National pride is a means of realizing the sanctity of the Motherland. National pride is a pure consciousness that beats together with our heart in our hearts. His charm and power are limitless. It is guided by intelligence. Intelligence is a great gift given to man by God. We oppose common sense to those who make various claims under the guise of human rights, freedom of speech, and democracy. We will never be able to get rid of ourselves because of other people's foreign values, promiscuous lifestyle, and artificial life standards. Our national pride does not allow such betrayal. Hypocrisy does not suit our nation. A person can be rich or poor, live well or badly, but without national pride, the meaning of life is lost.

Uzbekistan is a multi-ethnic country. That is why the national pride of any nation living on this earth is not humiliated. On the contrary, such a feeling is encouraged. First of all, this is the victory of our independence, peace, and national policy. In addition, it is the result of the rule of law in the state and non-state systems, in society. Undoubtedly, this opens the door to wide opportunities in building a civil society, implementing socio-economic, political, and legal reforms, further developing and strengthening our national statehood. From the day we took an independent step, until today, we relied on our own strength in creative work. We didn't depend on anyone, we didn't expect help or kindness from others. Despite this, we have achieved success in construction and beautification works, in various aspects of life, which are envied by friends and envied by enemies. In particular, we have made great progress in changing the appearance of our cities, building roads and bridges, developing motor transport, beautifying villages, repairing and restoring historical monuments, and large-scale beautification works.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev assessed the current processes in the world: "When we talk about the events in Palestine and Israel, the actions around the Al-Aqsa Mosque, we are only in favor of peace. "Of course, any issue can be resolved only by sitting around a table and making a compromise,"¹ they said.

While we are proud of our bold steps in the years of independence, we are certainly satisfied with our position in the world politics today. We went to the outside world with our courage, intelligence, independent step, prestige, and the weight of our contribution to world civilization. Today, we have our own strategic partners, reliable partners, close friends, and professional brothers in the world. That's why those who want to isolate us, humiliate us and put different labels on us have been left behind. Our peace is supported by the brave spirit of our ancestors, and as the power of our great nation shines, our Uzbekistan is more and more fascinating to the world. May such a charm protect our country, our peace, our destiny, our present and our future from evil eyes.

¹ <https://www.gazeta.uz/oz/2021/05/17/israel-palestine/> Date of application: April 24, 2024.